

Electromagnetic Scattering Simulations Using Overset Grids on Massively Parallel Computing Platforms

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Abstract

Overset grids are used in conjunction with a finite volume time domain (FVTD) Maxwell Equations solver to conduct electromagnetic scattering simulations on distributed memory massively parallel computing platforms. Simulation results are presented for two spheres in close proximity as well as a finned missile-like configuration. In addition, parallel performance data is presented for program runs on three modern parallel architectures. Results show the overset grid algorithm to be highly scalable and capable of producing results of comparable accuracy to single-grid solutions while greatly simplifying the often complex grid-generation process.

1. Introduction

Over the past several years, researchers from the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) community have begun to apply techniques developed for CFD to computational electromagnetics (CEM) problems. Specifically, they have drawn on the vast body of knowledge developed for solving hyperbolic systems of partial differential equations (PDEs) in an attempt to advance the state of the art in time domain simulations of electromagnetic phenomena governed by the Maxwell Equations. Their efforts have given birth to the FVTD methodology^{5,6}.

This work also brings to the CEM community a technique originally developed for CFD—the concept of overset or Chimera grids. This gridding scheme was originally developed by Benek, et al.¹ to simplify the often complex grid generation procedure required for a typical hyperbolic PDE solver. In this approach, a complex configuration is divided into a series of component geometries, and a body-conformal structured grid is generated around each component. The resulting grids are allowed to arbitrarily overlap and thereby combined to form a globally-unstructured grid. The cells comprising the grid are updated either via application of the discretized governing equation or by interpolation of information from surrounding cells. Although Yee¹⁰ has used overset grids with a staggered grid finite difference time domain algorithm, the methodology has gone largely unnoticed in the CEM community.

In addition to the benefits offered by overset grids, the present work seeks to exploit the capabilities of modern distributed memory parallel computing architectures. These machines typically possess massive amounts of memory and large numbers of processors thus making them ideal platforms for conducting large-scale CEM simulations. In order to extract a high level of performance from these machines, the computational domain is typically partitioned and assigned to the available processors in some fashion. The manner in which the computational domain is partitioned can have a dramatic effect on the parallel performance of an algorithm. To this end, techniques have been developed for efficiently dividing and mapping to the available processors a computational domain comprised of overset grids³. The combination of overset grids and parallel computing results in a technology that is both flexible and efficient, thus facilitating increasingly-complex electromagnetic scattering simulations.

2. Methodology

The cell-centered collocated FVTD methodology used in the present study solves the two Maxwell curl equations using a flux-vector splitting approach after Steger and Warming⁷ with a Monotone Upstream-centered Schemes for Conservation Laws (MUSCL) variable extrapolation technique after van Leer⁹. Time integration is performed via a two-stage Runge Kutta procedure to

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yield a numerical technique that is spatially third order and temporally second order accurate. Complete details of the numerical scheme can be found in references 2 and 5.

Prior to execution of the FVTD algorithm, the geometry must be generated, the interpolation stencils computed, and the domain partitioned for the desired parallel decomposition. The geometry generation process includes the creation of the computational grid as well as the identification of any surfaces for boundary conditions and radar cross section calculations. The generated grid is then input into PEGSUS, a program developed for computing interpolation stencils in an overset grid environment⁸. The output from PEGSUS along with the computational grid are then fed into the domain decomposition program which is able to partition a computational domain comprised of structured, unstructured, or overset grids for use on a distributed memory computing platform. Output from the domain decomposition algorithm serves as the input to the FVTD solver. The process is designed to be extremely flexible and requires little or no code modifications, even for radical changes in geometry.

3. Results

3.1. Scattering Simulations

Figure 1 shows a sample grid configuration for two perfectly electrically conducting (PEC) spheres of diameter one wavelength and a center-to-center separation distance of two wavelengths. The two spheres are each gridded with a body-conformal grid and then embedded within a uniform Cartesian background grid. While generating a single-zone structured grid for this geometry would be somewhat difficult, the overset grid approach allows for a simple grid generation procedure. The radar cross section (RCS) calculation for this geometry appears in Figure 2. The FVTD result agrees extremely well with the analytical solution computed via the generalized multipole technique⁴. This indicates that the errors associated with the interpolation process do not significantly impact the solution quality. Although not presented here, several grid cell densities were examined. Results indicate that the algorithm is relatively insensitive to grid cell density of the background grid² but is highly dependent on sufficient mesh resolution in the direction normal to the scattering surface. Indeed, experience has shown that, depending on the frequency of the incident wave, the wall spacing of the first cell must be between 100 and 2000 cells per wavelength.

A further demonstration of the utility of the overset grid approach is given by the geometry depicted in Figure 3 which shows the surface grids for a finned missile-like configuration. The fins are modeled as flat plates of finite thickness while the body is constructed from a circular cylinder with hemispherical end caps. Each of the fins is gridded independently of the body, and the fin grids are then embedded within the missile body grid as shown in Figure 4. Cells in the missile body grid which fall inside the fins are excluded from the computations. These cells are termed *hole cells* and are computed via PEGSUS prior to run time.

The validity of the tri-linear interpolation technique is demonstrated in Figure 5. Part *a* of the figure shows a single plane of one fin grid in conjunction with the local scattered electric field contours. Part *b* of Figure 5 contains the same information superimposed on top of the electric field contours of the missile body grid. Although the contours of the two grids agree in overall character, they do not match exactly. This is to be expected since the cell spacing of the two grids differs significantly and therefore the numerical errors associated with the FVTD scheme differ on each grid. The contours show regions of high scattering near the edges of the fin which is consistent with physical expectations.

3.2. Parallel Performance

The parallel performance of the algorithm has been assessed for a variety of grid sizes and problem types. Typical speedup and efficiency results are shown in parts *a* and *b*, respectively, of Figure 6. The presented results were obtained from program runs on the Intel Paragon, Cray T3D, and IBM SP2. Due to processor count and availability issues particular to each machine, the maximum number of processors used in the present work on each architecture was 128, 64, and 32, respectively. For the results shown, the total number of cells in the computational domain was approximately 166,000. Clearly, the algorithm scales very well, with efficiencies for the T3D and Paragon consistently above 90% even for this relatively small problem.

4. Conclusions

An overset grid FVTD solver designed for use on distributed architectures has been developed and tested. Results show the algorithm is capable of providing accurate results while greatly simplifying the geometry-generation process. Furthermore, the scheme has been demonstrated to achieve excellent parallel efficiencies on a variety of distributed architectures. Overall, the methodology shows great promise as a tool for conducting complex time domain scattering and wave propagation simulations.

References

- ¹ Benek, J. A., Steger, J. L. and Dougherty, F. C., "A Flexible Grid Embedding Technique with Application to the Euler Equations," AIAA Paper 83-1944, 1983.
- ² Blake, D. C. and Buter, T. A., "Overset Grid Methods Applied to a Finite-Volume Time-Domain Maxwell Equation Solver," AIAA Paper, 96-2338, 1996.
- ³ Blake, D. C., "Application of Unstructured Domain Decomposition Techniques to Overset Grids," 8th SIAM Conference for Parallel Processing for Scientific Computing, 13-18 Mar., 1997.
- ⁴ Liang, C. and Lo, Y. T., "Scattering by Two Spheres," *Radio Science*, vol. 2, no. 12, Dec. 1967.
- ⁵ Shang, J. S., "Characteristic-Based Algorithms for Solving the Maxwell Equations in the Time Domain," *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine*, vol. 37, no. 3, June 1995.
- ⁶ Shankar, V., Hall, W. and Mohammadian, A. H., "A CFD-Based Finite-Volume Procedure for Computational Electromagnetics - Interdisciplinary Applications of CFD Methods," AIAA Paper 89-1987, 1989.
- ⁷ Steger, J. L. and Warming, R. F., "Flux Vector Splitting of the Inviscid Gasdynamics Equations with Application to Finite Difference Methods," *Journal of Computational Physics*, vol. 40, pp. 263-93, Apr., 1981.
- ⁸ Suhs, N. E. and Tramel, R. W., "PEGSUS 4.0 User's Manual," AEDC-TR-91-8, Nov. 1991.
- ⁹ van Leer, B., "Flux-Vector Splitting for the Euler Equations," Technical Report 82-30, ICASE, Sept 1983.
- ¹⁰ Yee, K. S., Chen, J. S. and Chang, A. H., "Conformal Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) with Overlapping Grids," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 40, no. 9, Sept., 1992.

Figure 1: Dual sphere grid

Figure 2: Dual sphere RCS results

Figure 3: Finned missile surface grid

Figure 4: Finned missile Chimera grid

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Fin region scattered electric field contours: a) fin grid alone, b) fin and body grid

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: Parallel performance results: a) speedups, b) efficiencies